

1 Preparing the proposal I - Collecting information

Make explicit to yourself what you know and what you need to know about the journal and the publisher.

- If you need help in this task, use the long version of this support guide (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14512487](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14512487)).

2 Preparing the proposal II - Prepare an offer - Step 1

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Based on your findings during the preparation, draft a policy that best fits the needs of the publisher from your perspective.

Use our policy templates as a starting point:

- English Version: [10.5281/zenodo.13834305](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13834305)
- French Version: [10.5281/zenodo.13844144](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13844144)
- German Version: [10.5281/zenodo.13844164](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13844164)

3 Preparing the proposal III - Prepare an offer - Step 2

- Prepare arguments to convince the publisher: Why should they adopt a Green Open Access Policy?

- Think from the perspective of the publisher.
- You can find a list of helpful questions in our long support guide.

- Prepare also a BATNA (Best Alternative to Negotiated Agreement): For example, a short sentence that could be added to the journal imprint.

Negotiate - Step 1 - Making contact

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- Decide in advance how to contact the editor / publisher
- Contact a representative of the journal who is most likely in a position to decide on a self-archiving policy.
- Make up an appointment for a video-call or even a personal meeting.

5 Negotiate - Step 2 - Present your offer & look for an agreement

- Be concise:
 - Why do you suggest a policy? Explain the benefits for the journal.
 - How could it look like?
 - How can the policy be implemented?
 - Prepare a list of to dos for the publisher, libraries and authors.
 - Where can they publish the policy on their website?
 - Where can it be ingested (the GOAL database)?
- Close every meeting with a short summary of the next steps agreed on.
- Agree on deadlines.
- Take into account:
 - You might have to meet several times.
 - You might have to offer alternatives to your first offer.
 - It might take time for the editor or the editorial board to decide.

Make the results known: the GOAL Database

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- Once you have reached an agreement and the policy is publicly available, submit it to the GOAL-Database using the feedback form:
 - <https://goal.zhaw.ch/info/contact>

